

THE CREDIT-MODULE SYSTEM OF TRAINING IN ASSESSING STUDENTS' KNOWLEDGE AND THE IMPORTANCE OF PRACTICAL PROCESSES AS WELL AS THE CONVENIENCE CREATED BY THE CREDIT-MODULE SYSTEM

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Abstract. *In the conditions of innovative education, an innovative approach to the education system has become the demand of the time. Therefore, educational platforms and resources tested in international experience are used today in educational institutions of the Republic of Uzbekistan. In this article, according to foreign experience, the credit-module system, its role and importance in the processes of evaluating students' knowledge, and mainly the conveniences created by the credit-module system are included.*

Keywords: *credit-module system, credit, module, assessment of student knowledge, module technology, curriculum, curriculum.*

Today, in our social life, which is witnessing rapid developments, paying close attention to the education system is one of the most important tasks. Also, the issue of raising the quality of education to a higher level and improving it is important because of its urgency. For this reason, a number of reforms are being implemented in the education system at the same time. The experience of developed countries clearly proves that reforms in education will have a great effect in the future.

Today, in the Republic of Uzbekistan, the introduction of new management systems in the field of education, the development of the level of organization of the educational process based on world experience, the improvement of the quality of education and the development of the responsibility of specialists in the future have become an urgent issue. The decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated January 28, 2022 "On the development strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026" approved by No. PF-60 and In order to ensure the implementation of the decisions of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 824 of December 31, 2020 "On measures to improve the system related to the organization of the educational process in higher education institutions", higher education The credit-module system has been gradually introduced in educational institutions. Digital technologies and modern teaching methods are included in the higher education processes in the "Concept of the Development of the Higher Education System of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030", approved by the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-5847 of October 8, 2019 introduction, widespread involvement of young people in scientific activities, combating corruption, increasing the share of students studying engineering and technical education, introducing the credit-module system, training programs aimed at increasing practical skills specific tasks for increasing the share of practical training have been defined. After this decree was adopted, work on the gradual transfer of the higher education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan to the credit-module system began. Based on the decisions of the President of the Republic of December 24, 2021 "On additional

measures to ensure the academic and organizational-management independence of state higher education institutions" and "On measures to provide financial independence to state higher education institutions" from January 2022 This system was introduced in 35 higher education institutions.

Until today, there was no unit of measure that would systematically assess the progress of students of higher education institutions operating in the country, their formation as specialists, and that would be understandable to everyone. For this reason, the credit-module system, first of all, is much more perfect, modern, and most importantly, all (parents, learners, educators, management of the educational organization) to the higher education system in the country.) introduced a unit of measurement that is understandable for.

The credit-module system is a process of educational organization and is an assessment model based on a collection of module technologies and credit measurement. Carrying it out as a whole is a complex and systematic process. In the credit-module principle, two main issues are important:

- ensuring independent work of students;
- assessment of student knowledge based on rating.

Based on this, it can be said that according to the credit-module system, the educational programs of higher education institutions are divided into different disciplines and modules aimed at specific learning outcomes. It was envisaged that each subject or module would be represented in a certain number of credits depending on the amount of study load. For example, each subject may represent 5, 6, or 7.5 credits in the average. It was determined that students must collect a certain amount of credits every semester and academic year, and after collecting the appropriate number of credits, they will be awarded a bachelor's or master's degree.

Among these, it was found permissible to recognize the following as the main tasks of the credit module system:

- organization of educational processes on the basis of modules;
- determining the value of one subject (module), course (credit);
- assessment of students' knowledge based on rating points;
- to enable students to create their own study plans individually;
- increase the share of independent education in the educational process;
- the convenience of educational programs and the ability to change based on the demand for a specialist in the labor market.

All of these recognitions require not only teaching based on innovative educational technologies, but also a unique and new attitude to the student's independent study, research, and educational process, i.e. based on the demand of the current labor market, it is necessary and deeply oriented. The main point of attention is that it is aimed at ensuring the education of a person throughout his life and forming human capital that can meet the labor market and modern requirements.

It is here that it is important to dwell on the essence of the module and credit concepts. Because it is not an exaggeration to say that this is the most urgent point of this issue.

"Credit (credit) is a unit of measurement of the educational load spent on studying and mastering subjects in a particular educational field or program. A credit is also the minimum amount of time students are allowed to study in classrooms and independently, usually one week. Credit is given to a student after completing the assigned assignments in a specific subject and

successfully passing the final exam. It is envisaged that each student will accumulate credits in order to obtain a diploma in the field and specialty of his choice in the future.

It should be emphasized that loans are not just numbers. Each credit represents a certain amount of study load that the student must complete and that the student has achieved certain learning outcomes as a result. Only by completing these downloads can one earn a certain number of credits in that subject. The implementation of this system in higher education will increase the quality of teaching, ensure transparency, eliminate corruption, reveal the true knowledge of the learner, and create a foundation for the student to study and work independently.

A module is a part of the curriculum in which several subjects and courses are studied, several subjects (courses) are aimed at students to acquire certain knowledge and skills, and the capacity for analytical and logical observation.) is a set. In this, the teacher organizes the educational process, gives live, video and audio lectures, coordinates and monitors the student's activities. It is assumed that the student will study the subject independently and perform the assigned tasks independently.

According to international experience, the educational process in the credit-module system consists of 2-4 modules per semester. The subjects included in the module are formed from easy to complex, from theoretical-methodical subjects to applied subjects and based on the principle of logical complementarity. In order for a student to become a mature specialist in the field he is studying, he needs not only information, but also the ability to process it and put it into practice.

The introduction of the credit-module system became an important factor in the cooperation between the teacher and the student. In modular education, the pedagogue organizes, manages, advises and checks the student's learning process. The student moves independently towards the directed object. The greatest emphasis is placed on independent education of students.

Through the credit-module system, the importance of independent education in the educational process is also observed, and as a result, it will lead to an increase in the independence, creative initiative and activity of specialists in the future. Also, in the credit-module system, students of any type of higher education institution will always have the opportunity to receive help and advice from teachers and peers. This strengthens mutual solidarity and serves to form teamwork skills.

The transition to the credit-module teaching system will increase both the obligation and the demand for professors and teachers of the higher educational institution. As mentioned above, with the modular teaching system, the teacher performs not only the functions of an informant and supervisor, but also the functions of a consultant and coordinator. With its help, the leadership role of the teacher in the pedagogical process is preserved.

Therefore, it can be concluded from the above that the credit system of Education increases the exchange of students. Because the credits received in one higher education institution are taken into account in the other, and students can transfer from one higher education institution to another without losing credits. It is this system that allows Uzbek students to continue their studies in advanced foreign higher education institutions and to remove complex bureaucratic obstacles.

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